

Investigation of tool/part interaction effects in the manufacture of composite components.

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SUMMARY: In order for composite components of reliably consistent geometry to be manufactured it is necessary to understand the many factors that can lead to geometrical variability being seen in the cured parts. One element of this that has been identified as having a potentially major influence is the interaction between the tool and the uncured lay-up when the tool's expansion coefficient is different from that of the composite lay-up. However, it has proven very difficult to study these issues, and much simulation work is based on the use of simple semi-empirical models of limited applicability. The work reported here is a part of ongoing studies at the University of Bristol, aimed at providing an in-depth understanding of the processes occurring during cure to better inform modelling and simulation activities. The work uses two new approaches, the use of enforced interaction between tooling and lay-up and the direct measurement of the strains induced in the lay-up by that interaction.

KEYWORDS: Variability, tool interactions, manufacturing

INTRODUCTION

All manufacturing operations tend to produce components that display some level of variability in the geometry of the parts. In most cases this variability can be constrained to close tolerances by the application of suitable material and process controls such that the design intent, as manifest in the design drawings, can be achieved without trial and error. In the case of parts made from advanced composite material cured at elevated temperatures this is often not the case and a substantial investment in iterations of the tooling geometry may be needed to ensure that the mean component geometry is as required. Even when this state has been achieved it is by no means uncommon that the variation from part to part on that mean geometry is greater than would be ideal.

There are many identified mechanisms that might generate these differences between tool and part geometry, and the associated variability. These include variability in the materials of construction such as unidirectional prepreg, [1], variation of fibre content through thickness [2], variation in expansion coefficients [3], variation in lay-up quality, variation in consolidation including bridging and wrinkling [4], and interactions between the tooling and the lay-up. This paper is principally related to the interaction between the tooling and the lay-up, however some comments will also be made about the variability in the unidirectional prepreg used. Interaction between tooling and lay-up has been extensively studied [5,6,7,8], but the conclusions as to the extent and importance of the effect vary widely. For example, [5] showed very substantial curvature in long, flat, thin unidirectional strips after curing, whereas [6] concluded that only a

very small part, if any, of the overall distortion in 0.90 unsymmetrical strips could be ascribed to a tool interaction effect.

The mechanism put forward leading to tool interaction effects is as follows. Differences in thermal expansion coefficients (CTE) between tooling and reinforcement laid on to that tooling lead to interfacial stresses being set up as the tooling is heated to cure the part. These interfacial stresses may then give rise to a strain in the reinforcement ply adjacent to the tool surface and a stress gradient may then arise through the thickness of the part, becoming “locked-in” at the end of the cure process. Such a “locked-in” stress gradient will then generate a warpage when the part is removed from the tooling as the internal strain energy in the part seeks a minimum solution. It is thus axiomatic that there is a difference in CTE between tool and lay-up for a tool interaction effect to be seen. Whilst invar, graphite or composite tools may be used to minimise these effects it is commonplace to use materials such as aluminium or steel in tooling, for a wide variety of reasons, such as cost, lead time, multiple suppliers, robustness, etc.

The work reported here was carried out in three strands. The first was to measure the curvature of thin, flat, unidirectional carbon fibre laminates moulded under various moulding conditions. Whilst some curvature was seen in the majority of mouldings, the level of curvature was low and substantially less than some of the results presented in the literature such as [5]. The second strand was to develop a method of ensuring a strain gradient through the thickness and use this to assess the importance of some of the processing factors in the development of warpage. The technique used was to wrap a prepreg ply completely around an aluminium tool overlapping the ply on one side of the tool. A stress gradient must then occur in the region of overlap, unless all the induced stresses in the prepreg are relieved during the processing. The last area discussed is the development of a method of measuring the strains induced in the prepreg by the tool expansion throughout the whole process cycle from uncured prepreg to cured and demoulded part. Results from this method, were applied to thin, flat, unidirectional carbon fibre laminates, and enabled the results obtained in the initial series of mouldings to be correctly interpreted. This paper is essentially a snapshot of this work at the point of writing and further development is ongoing.

THIN, FLAT, STRIP LAMINATE EXPERIMENTS

The laminates were manufactured by autoclave moulding using the prepreg manufacturer’s recommended cure cycle, on an aluminium tool 10mm thick, with a layer of A5000 FEP film between tool and lay-up and between tool and the breather cloth. The tool was supported in the autoclave in such a way as to ensure that it stayed flat during curing. Samples were made with the tool plate both ways up to ensure that the plate was stable during cure. The unidirectional prepreg material used was AS4-8552 at 0.25mm/ply thickness, supplied by Hexcel. The material was cured by a zero bleed technique to ensure that, as far as possible, induced fibre volume fraction gradients were avoided during the cure process. Samples were made at 500mm and 1000mm long and 50mm wide and generally at 4 or 8 ply thicknesses. Cured samples were measured for thickness and any curvature was established, the samples were then trimmed 1cm off each edge and the curvature measurement was repeated.

Curvature was generally rather small and the development of a technique was needed to allow its measurement. The method used was to stand the strips on edge on a sheet of paper and use a paint spray to transfer the edge geometry to the paper with minimal force. This technique proved to give reproducible results and was adopted for all the results quoted here. Four 500mm long samples were subjected to a moisture absorption cycle to a weight gain of approximately 1% and their curvature was remeasured. There was no change in curvature as a result of this treatment, indicating that the curvatures were not thermoelastic in origin, and supporting the

view that the curvature could be being generated by tool interactions. Figs 1 and 2 show the measured shapes of the 1000mm long specimens for 4 and 8 ply laminates respectively for the first four experimental runs.

Fig 1. Sample geometry for 4 ply specimens

Fig 2. Sample geometry for 8 ply specimens

The most obvious feature in these data is that the variability between experimental runs is very significant. Runs 1 and 3 used the front face of the tool and runs 2 and 4 used the back face, but there are no consistent differences due to this effect. Evidence from another part of the programme at the University of Bristol showed that the prepreg being used exhibited a consistent difference in weight/unit area across the width of the sheet of prepreg. Runs 1 to 4 had not taken this into account and had used randomly selected strips of prepreg. Two more samples were then manufactured at 4 ply and 1000mm long. One used four plies taken from the middle of the width of the roll and the other used four plies taken from the edge of the roll. These were processed in exactly the same way as the previous samples and the shapes of these samples are shown in fig 3, also shown in fig 3 is the same data as seen in fig 1.

Fig 3. Sample geometry for selected prepreg specimens

With the exception of the single specimen that showed reverse curvature, the 4 ply results all fell between the limits set by the two specimens that used prepreg selected from different positions across the roll. Cross-sectional studies showed that the fibre distribution was not uniform within the plies, and that a thin resin-rich zone could be detected at the tool surface. Simple FEA modelling taking into account the presence of a resin rich zone and varying fibre

volume fraction suggested that the curvatures seen and their variation could be accounted for by similar levels of prepreg variability and resin richness to those seen experimentally.

The conclusion from this activity using flat laminates was that curvature could be detected, and that the curvature was non-thermoelastic and generally in the expected convex-up direction for a tool interaction effect. However, the variation in the level of curvature was dominated by prepreg selection effects, and its mean level could be simulated using reasonable values of tool face resin rich zone and volume fraction variation. The existence of a general tool interaction effect could not, therefore, be inferred from the results on long, flat UD strip laminates.

FORCED INTERACTION EXPERIMENTS

The forced interaction experiments used a sample as shown in fig 4.

Fig 4. Forced interaction set up

The forced interaction tool consisted of a 10mm thick, 10cm wide and 50cm long aluminium plate with rounded ends (5mm radius) around which a single 5 cm wide ply of prepreg could be wrapped such that it overlapped on the lower surface. The tool was then used in one of three ways. It was firstly used as shown in fig 4, mounted on a 10mm thick aluminium tool plate, prepared as in the previous experimental series and bagged down to that plate (type 1). Other runs were carried out with the tool envelope bagged on its own (type 2). The tool was used bagged down to the aluminium plate for autoclave runs and enveloped bagged for vacuum only runs in an oven.

The shape of the moulded loops was easier to measure than for the UD flat strips as the distortions tended to be much greater. Use was made of a photocopier to provide an image of the edge that could readily be measured.

The typical shape of an autoclave moulded specimen is as shown in fig 5.

Fig 5. Typical shape of an autoclave moulded specimen

When the shape had been identified in the as-moulded condition the sample was separated into one ply and two ply mouldings by cutting through at the two ends. The shape of the overlap side was not greatly influenced by this separation. However, the 1 ply side generally showed a

considerable deviation from a flat laminate after cutting, exhibiting a pronounced curvature away from the tool at the two ends of the specimen.

Fig 6 shows the shape of typical mouldings after separation and edge trimming, for runs carried out in the autoclave under pressure (6 bar) and vacuum only (1 bar) runs.

Fig 6. The geometry of typical autoclave mouldings produced with pressure and vacuum only

A positive warpage is defined here a convex side up relative to the tool surface, (i.e. with a gap between the tool and the part in the centre) and a negative warpage is defined as convex side down (i.e. with a gap between the tool and part at the ends).

One of the most striking features of the geometry is the high level of curvature seen on the single ply side. This curvature is very similar for both cases shown here. The direction of the curvature is in the opposite sense to that seen with flat laminates and the curvature is of much greater magnitude. An examination of the component suggests a mechanism by which this curvature may be generated. The inner radii of the two corner regions are both seen to have very wavy fibres on the surface. Such wavy fibres arise essentially from bending the prepreg around the 5mm radius. In doing this, the innermost fibres must buckle under the applied compressive loads. Any fibre tension that is carried by the prepreg around the radius must then be carried only in the outermost fibres, generating a strain gradient through the ply at the start of the nominally flat part of the moulding. This strain gradient will be reduced towards the mid-length

of the moulding, but the strain equalisation within the ply is expected to take place over several hundred times the thickness of the ply.

On the two ply side of the moulding the shape is more complex having both concave and convex regions relative to the tool. The mechanism driving the generation of this shape is as outlined in fig 7.

Fig 7. Schematic of mechanism of geometry generation in two ply case

At the end of each ply there must be zero tension, which will build up along the length of the ply. The curvature will then be in the direction of the surface that is carrying the highest tension at each point. An unequal build up of tension in the two plies will lead to an asymmetry about the mid-point of the samples, as is seen in all the samples. Asymmetry may also be caused by the superimposition of the convex down curvature seen on the single ply side onto the complex curvature on the two ply side, this can be seen in fig 9.

Samples moulded in an oven under vacuum only conditions, envelope bagged without the secondary aluminium plate, show much less curvature on the overlap side and the wave-like distortion seen in the other specimens is less pronounced, see fig 8.

Fig 8. The geometry of envelope bagged mouldings produced with vacuum only

Decreasing the overlap length to 160mm under the same vacuum-only moulding conditions would be expected to lead to a lower level of interaction stresses and thus a reduction in warpage in the overlap region, and this is borne out in practice as shown in fig 9.

Fig 9. The geometry of envelope bagged mouldings produced with a reduced overlap length

The overlap region in the centre of the specimen's length shows the wave-like behaviour seen before, but the outer regions show the curvature away from the tool that is typical of all the specimens in single ply regions.

The curvature produced in the overlap region clearly depends on the level of force required to shear the two layers over each other. Increasing the pressure [fig 6] or the overlap [fig 8 cf fig 9] increases the curvature, as does sandwiching the overlap region between two aluminium tool faces [as shown in fig 4] rather than having one toolface and one bag face [fig 6 cf fig 8]. This last effect may be due to the two sheets of aluminium establishing an essentially fixed gap between them such that point to point variations in the fibre weight/unit area of the prepreg have a greater influence on the shear forces. The samples with the highest levels of curvature on the overlap side show more than an order of magnitude more distortion than the samples with the lowest levels of curvature. By contrast the curvature on the single ply side is much less variable, only about a factor of two being seen between the highest and lowest levels of curvature. The mechanism responsible for this curvature seems to be tied up with the wrinkling of fibres around the radius and the development of a stress gradient through the ply. It should be noted that the mean level of strain in the ply (which would be expected to be very different from case to case) leads to no curvature in itself.

INSTRUMENTED PLY EXPERIMENTS

The experiments with long flat UD strip laminates suggested that little or no interaction with the tool was taking place, by contrast the experiments with the forced interaction tool showed that very considerable interactions could be generated without great difficulty. To understand these results better it would be useful to have some technique available that would permit the build-up of stresses and strains in the fibres of the prepreg to be monitored directly. This is difficult to achieve because of the problems inherent in trying to attach sensors of any sort to uncured prepreg. The approach taken here has been to cure a series of small spots on a strip of prepreg and then to bond a strain gauge to each spot. The variability inherent in the prepreg in terms of both local fibre content and fibre straightness is such that it was found to be necessary to calibrate each strip of prepreg prior to use. The procedure used is outlined below.

A series of trial spot cures was carried out to establish a temperature and time that gave a good cure with a minimal progress of the cure outside the spot area. These conditions were a set

temperature of 250°C, applied for 5 minutes under a load equating to a 10bar pressure for the 8mm diameter spot. The spot-curing set-up is shown schematically in fig 10. Following the spot-curing a strain gauge was attached to each of three spots (see fig 11) with a high temperature adhesive, which was cured using the spot-cure rig for 5minutes at 220°C to avoid problems with the adhesive softening and then curing during the prepreg cure run.

Fig 10. Schematic of the spot cure rig

Before the sample could be used in a moulding the strain gauges needed to be ‘calibrated’ for load. This was achieved by curing the ends of the strips between hot plates to allow them to be gripped in the test machine and logging the strains as load was slowly applied at room temperature. A load of 1kN was applied, which for the 50mm wide strip of 0.25mm thick prepreg equates to a nominal stress of 80MPa. Fig 11 shows the strain gauge outputs from this test.

Fig 11. Nominal ply stress versus strain for uncured prepreg.

The three dashed lines are the data from the three strain gauges (labelled as they appear when the sample is mounted in the test machine). The thin solid lines though those data are polynomial fit lines that act as the calibration curves that may later be used on the raw data from the cure experiment. The dotted line represents the sort of response that might be expected from a uniform sample that was fully cured. It can be seen that in the cases of the middle and bottom gauges the response at the highest stress levels is becoming parallel to this cured laminate line. There are two effects that can be seen at work in figure 11. The first is that the tows are not entirely straight so that there is a substantial lead in before the strains start to become more linear with load. Equally, in any cross section some tows are straighter than others and will pick up load preferentially. The other is that there are point to point variations in fibre content and alignment potentially leading to differences in the effective load response of each cured spot. After cure the calibration loading was repeated and at that time the lead in was eliminated,

although the stiffness differences were not. The uncured load/strain calibration was used to correct the raw strain data to the end of the cure cycle and the fully cured data was used to correct the raw strain data during the cool down phase. Due to the necessity for the calibration and the size limitations of available test machines the length of the strip used in these experiments was 650mm. Fig 12 shows the corrected strain data against time for a single ply experiment and figure 13 shows the corrected strain data against time for a four ply experiment with the strain in the top ply being monitored. Fig 12 also shows the output of a strain gauge on the aluminium tool, which effectively shows the temperature of the tool. Several things can be noted from fig 12. Firstly the strains in the two outer gauges are very similar, without the correction the strains in the two outermost gauges show distinctly different readings.

Fig 12. Strain development during cure for a single ply specimen

The strain development generally follows the tool's expansion, apart from a small relaxation of strain at the start of the dwell and cure holds, with a final strain being measured as about 40% of the strain in the tool. The measured strains are substantial and are rather at odds with the lack of any great curvature in the long strip experiments considered earlier. The four ply experiment was conducted to throw some light on why those previous experiments showed so low a warpage. Fig 13 shows the strain development for that test, with the same temperature profile.

Fig 13. Strain development during cure for a four ply specimen

This test gave a peak strain very close to a quarter of the value seen in the one ply experiment. This low absolute strain level may also go some way to explaining the lack of exact correspondence between the two outer gauges, although these may also be caused by local differences in stress transfer between the plies. Although the two outer gauges are not in exact correspondence the ratio between centre and outer strain readings is very similar for one ply and four ply cases. These features of the data suggest that the strain in the four ply specimen is

relatively uniformly distributed and that there is little strain gradient through the thickness. This is consistent with the lack of any substantial curvature seen in the long flat UD specimens with a thickness of 4 ply. Any slip between subsequent plies through the stack of four plies would have been expected to lead to a strain gradient through the thickness and, hence to a curvature, the absence of the curvature gives confidence that strain gradients are absent and that the results of the spot cure experiments are being properly interpreted.

CONCLUSIONS

The results from curing long and narrow strips of UD prepreg against an aluminium tool suggested that little or no tool interaction effect was present. Measurement of the actual strains developed in the prepreg during cure by a new technique involving localised spot curing of the prepreg shows that very substantial strains are actually developed in strips of prepreg during cure, up to an effective stress of 250MPa in a single ply. However, for the prepreg and configuration studied no significant through thickness strain gradient is generated by the strains in the prepreg induced by the tool expansion. The spot cure method has been demonstrated to be effective in allowing the strains induced during the cure to be monitored. The method requires that the strain gauged spots be calibrated by being loaded in tension to account for the variabilities in the prepreg. Further development of the technique is ongoing and the method will be applied to the study of the stresses in plies that are associated with consolidation and bridging effects, as well as to tool interaction effects. The forced interaction tool approach provides a ready way of studying the tool interaction forces by ensuring that a strain gradient can be enforced. It provides a test bed for the study of the mechanisms leading to tool interaction stresses and distortions, and a test case for the predictive approaches being developed within the broader ongoing programme at the University of Bristol. Future work will include bringing together the two techniques outlined here and a broader set of experiments utilising the forced interaction approach.

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